

TWO-STEP IMPLICIT PISMAN-RICKFORD SCHEME FOR SOLVING THE LAPLACE EQUATION

Abduxamidov Sardor Kaxarboyevich
M.T. Urazbayeva

Intern of the Laboratory "Mechanics of Fluid, Gas and Hydraulic Drive Systems" of the Institute of Mechanics and Seismic Resistance of Structures.

AS RUz,

E-mail: sardor.abdukhamidov@mail.ru

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ABSTRACT

An analysis was made of determining the stationary temperature field in a solid body. For this, the Peaceman-Rickford finite-difference scheme is used [1]. To solve the elliptic equation, a two-step finite-difference scheme is used.

Introduction: The Laplace equations is a model equation for elliptic partial differential equations. In the Cartesian coordinate system, the two-dimensional Laplace equation has the form

$$\frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial y^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Some important problems are solved using an elliptic partial differential equation. Problems of calculating subsonic irrotational (potential) gas flow and determining the stationary temperature field in a solid body. Numerical method Consider the problem of temperature propagation in a pipe. In this case, equation (1) will take the following form

$$\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} = 0 \quad (2)$$

Let us now turn to the study of the two-step finite difference Peaceman-Rickford scheme for solving the Laplace equation.

Step1.

$$T_{i,j}^{n+1/2} = T_{i,j}^n + \rho_n (\partial_x^2 T_{i,j}^{n+1/2} + \partial_y^2 T_{i,j}^n)$$

Step2.

$$T_{i,j}^{n+1} = T_{i,j}^{n+1/2} + \rho_n (\partial_x^2 T_{i,j}^{n+1/2} + \partial_y^2 T_{i,j}^{n+1})$$

where $\partial_x^2 T_{i,j}^{n+1/2}$, $\partial_y^2 T_{i,j}^n$ and $\partial_y^2 T_{i,j}^{n+1}$ are expressed as follows

$$\partial_x^2 T_{i,j}^{n+1/2} = \frac{T_{i+1,j}^{n+1/2} - 2T_{i,j}^{n+1/2} + T_{i-1,j}^{n+1/2}}{\Delta x^2}$$

$$\partial_y^2 T_{i,j}^{n+1} = \frac{T_{i,j+1}^{n+1} - 2T_{i,j}^{n+1} + T_{i,j-1}^{n+1}}{\Delta y^2}$$

$$\partial_y^2 T_{i,j}^n = \frac{T_{i,j+1}^n - 2T_{i,j}^n + T_{i,j-1}^n}{\Delta y^2}$$

Calculation result.

Figure 1. The result of the implicit Peaceman-Rickford method is displayed. 1.

The Peaceman-Rickford method.

Fig1.

Conclusion. As a result of the calculation, it is shown that the distribution of temperature in a solid. It can be seen that,

on the lower layers of the pipe, the temperature propagates in an irrotational flow.

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